

Biomechanical study of the shoulder joint complex and associated injuries

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Abstract

The glenohumeral joint allows the arm to perform countless and varied movements. This diversity generates a vulnerability on the joint, which, in turn, tends to suffer dislocations, affecting 1-2% of the population. In addition, individuals who frequently perform activities such as swimming, baseball, tennis, among others, are more likely to have shoulder injuries due to the stress to which their joints and muscles are subjected. It is also known that, given a first dislocation, it may lead to the appearance of lesions in the structures that make up the shoulder joint complex, causing some patients to suffer from recurrent dislocations. This can be due to the inaccurate information available regarding the most appropriate treatment for each situation. It is important to note that a proper treatment should allow the patient to regain glenohumeral joint stability without causing pain and reducing mobility. The development of this work aims to contribute to a better understanding of the shoulder complex, and thus provide relevant clinical information, allowing clinicians to perceive the most appropriate treatments with greater ease and confidence, ensuring that the patient will not suffer from instability in the glenohumeral joint again. A finite element model was built for this study, which allowed a biomechanical analysis of the shoulder complex. This work allowed to verify the importance of the stabilizing role of the glenohumeral ligaments with the humerus positioned in the upper ranges. In addition, it was possible to conclude that glenoid defects with sizes greater than 37.5% of the glenoid width combined with any defect in the humeral head should be repaired with a Latarjet procedure.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4843511

Article Info

Keywords

Finite element method
Anterior dislocation
Bankart lesions
Hill-Sachs lesions
Biomechanics

Article History

Received: 12/01/2021
Revised: 26/03/2021
Accepted: 05/05/2021

1 Introduction

The shoulder enables the performance of a wide range of different movements such as flexion, extension, abduction, adduction, external and internal rotation. In case any of its structures gets injured, it can lead to weakness, pain or instability [1]. It has been reported that 1-2% of the general population will experience a glenohumeral dislocation [2]. Besides, it was reported that glenohumeral dislocations in the anterior direction correspond to 98% of all shoulder dislocations [3].

Bankart and Hill-Sachs lesions result from anterior dislocations and are quite individualized, which means that these can have different sizes and locations. Besides, there is also a wide variety of treatments and little certainty as to which will be the most suitable for each situation. Consequently, the recurrence rate for the treatment including immobilization and physical therapy can exceed 70%, and the recurrence rate following surgical repair has been reported to be up to 17.5%. In addition, for patients that are subjected to surgical repair, these may experience joint stiffness and reduced range of motion [4].

The aim of this work is to better understand the mechanisms of the shoulder complex and the aetiology of shoulder instability, attempting to establish a validated algorithm that makes it easier to choose the most appropriate treatment for each situation, providing stability without limiting the range of motion and, consequently, decreasing the recurrence rates. More specifically, it focuses on evaluating the stability of the glenohumeral joint with the presence of the Bankart and Hill-Sachs defects simultaneously, since it was reported that the recurrence is usually associated with the presence of both lesions [5].

1.1. Bankart and Hill-Sachs lesions

Anterior dislocations usually occur with the humerus in the apprehension position (60° abducted and 60° externally rotated) [6]. These may lead to permanent deformation of the glenohumeral ligaments, antero-inferior labral lesions and bony injuries that consequently result in recurrent instability.

A Bankart lesion consists of the detachment of the antero-inferior section of the labrum and may also involve bone loss. A study reported that these lesions occur in up to 95% of the shoulders that had a dislocation [7].

Another common shoulder injury is the Hill-Sachs lesion which can be defined as a cortical depression in the postero-superior section of the humeral head. These were reported to occur in up to 90% of shoulders that had a dislocation [7].

1.2. Treatments

Treatment may involve non-surgical rehabilitation or surgical repair. The first approach usually involves an immobilization period of approximately 3 weeks and it is followed by a rehabilitation period, in which the patient gradually returns to daily activities [8]. Surgical techniques are used when the injury is more severe, and these include anatomic or intracapsular repairs, which attempt to repair and reinsert the labrum and the ligaments in their original position (e.g. Bankart repair) and nonanatomic or extracapsular repairs, which consist of reconstructing the glenohumeral joint with a bone block (e.g. Bristow or Latarjet procedures) or with a soft tissue block (e.g. Putti-Platt or Magnuson-Stack procedures) [9].

Worldwide, Bankart repair accounts for almost 90% of primary surgeries for anterior instability. However, in France 72% of surgeons prefer the Latarjet repair as a primary surgery for instability [4].

Besides, the current literature lacks comprehensive comparative studies, in other words, there are studies suggesting that glenoid critical bone loss should be lower than 20% of the glenoid width [10], while others suggest that it is 21% [11] and 25% [12]. Regarding Hill-Sachs defects, while a study suggests that it is recommended treatment for defects with sizes bigger than 37.5% of the diameter of the humeral head [13], another suggests treatment for defects with size greater than 31.25% [14]. Finally, for combined defects, a study suggested that at least one of the defects should be addressed with a bony reconstruction for defects of 10-20% of the glenoid width combined with defects of 19% of the humeral head diameter [3]. It was also reported that a bony procedure should be performed when there is a glenoid bone loss greater than 20% and an engaging Hill-Sachs lesion [15]. In addition, [16] suggested that glenoid defects smaller than 25% combined with a non-engaging Hill-Sachs lesion should undergo arthroscopic Bankart repair, while if combined with an engaging Hill-Sachs lesion the patient should also be subjected to a *remplissage*; If the glenoid defects are greater than 25% a Latarjet procedure should be performed for a non-engaging Hill-Sachs lesion, and a Latarjet combined with a *remplissage*/bone graft should be performed for an engaging Hill-Sachs lesion.

2 Methodology

To determine the effect of combined injuries in shoulder stability, a finite element model was created. This model includes the humerus, the scapula and their respective cartilages as done by Walia et al, 15 [17]. Besides, it was added the synovial liquid and the glenohumeral capsule and ligaments.

From a set of medical images obtained from CT (computerized tomography), 3D models of the humerus and the scapula were created, using the Mimics software (v20).

Then, the model was imported into the 3-Matic software (v12) to create the mesh. It is known that as the size of finite elements tends to zero, the solution obtained converges to the exact solution. However, in order not to get too heavy files, a mesh with triangles with sides measuring approximately 0.0025 m was created and the surfaces of the glenoid and humeral head that will have contact conditions have been assigned with a more refined mesh (0.0014 m).

In Femap (v11.4.1) the articular cartilages were modelled. The main function of cartilage is to reduce friction and promote good contact between the bones. Cartilage was created as having a thickness of 0.0015 m, however since the thickness of the cartilage on the humeral head and glenoid is not uniform, the simulations will begin by promoting the fit between these two surfaces.

Solidworks was used to construct the structure of the glenohumeral capsule. According to literature, it is more appropriate to consider the capsule as a continuous sheet, instead of several discrete structures [18].

The mesh of the capsule was created in Abaqus (2019). As shown in Fig.1 the posterior section has only one layer (red) since it is thinner, and the section of the capsule which is reinforced by the ligaments has two layers (red and blue). After the mesh was ready, pressure was applied to the inferior section of the capsule to recreate the insertion of the IGHL (Inferior Glenohumeral Ligament) into the anatomical neck of the humerus in a U- or V- shape, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 – FEM developed for this work.

The positions that were chosen as the initial positions to run the simulations were with the humerus at 45° or 90° humero-thoracic abduction and neutral rotation, 40° of external rotation or 60° external rotation.

2.1. Creation of defects

The size of the defects was chosen based on [3] for the humeral head and [11] for the glenoid and are shown in table 1 and the defects made are shown in Fig. 2.

Table 1 – Sizes of the defects

	Humerus defect size (% of the diameter of the humeral head)	Glenoid defect size (% of the glenoid width)
Defect 1	0.00238 m (6%)	0.00434 m (12,5%)
Defect 2	0.00753 m (19%)	0.00868 m (25%)
Defect 3	0.01228 m (31%)	0.01302 m (37,5%)
Defect 4	0.01743 m (44%)	0.01736 m (50%)

Fig. 2 – Bankart and Hill-Sachs defects created in this work.

2.2. Material Properties

Bones were assumed to be rigid bodies since bone deformation is almost negligible when compared to soft tissues and to reduce computational cost, while the articular cartilage was modelled as a Neo-Hookean hyperelastic, incompressible material [17], [19].

To study the behaviour of glenohumeral ligaments and following the suggestions of previous studies [18], a hyperelastic constitutive model - Holzapfel-Gasser-Ogden (HGO) - was used. Besides, it was added a numerical damage parameter to represent the behaviour of the ligaments more accurately.

In the HGO model, the strain energy density function is defined as:

$$\Psi = \Psi_{vol} + \Psi_{mat} + \Psi_{fib} \quad (1)$$

where Ψ_{mat} corresponds to the contribution of the matrix, Ψ_{fib} corresponds to the contribution of the fibers and Ψ_{vol} imposes the incompressible behaviour of the material.

More, Ψ_{vol} , Ψ_{mat} , Ψ_{fib} are expressed as:

$$\Psi_{vol} = \frac{1}{D} \left(\frac{(J^{el})^2 - 1}{2} - \ln J^{el} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\Psi_{mat} = C_{10}(\bar{I}_1 - 3) \quad (3)$$

$$\Psi_{fib} = \frac{k_1}{2k_2} \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \{ \exp[k_2 \langle \bar{E}_\alpha \rangle^2] - 1 \} \quad (4)$$

with

$$\bar{E}_\alpha = k(\bar{I}_1 - 3) + (1 - 3k)(\bar{I}_{4(\alpha\alpha)} - 1), \quad (5)$$

where C_{10} , D , k_1 and k_2 are material coefficients.

N is the number of fiber families, which was assumed in this work to be $N = 1$, and k is a parameter that controls the dispersion of the fibers around the mean direction (it can have a value between 0 and 1/3 - if $k = 0$ it means the fibres are perfectly aligned in the preferential direction, whereas if $k = 1/3$ it means that the fibres are randomly distributed).

$\bar{I}_1$ is the first strain invariant and $\bar{I}_{4(\alpha\alpha)}$ are pseudo-invariants of the deviatoric part of the right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor.

To define the preferential direction of the fibres it was adapted a Matlab routine from [20]. This created a vector at the centroid of each element defining the orientation of the fibres.

The HGO constitutive model, despite describing the material properties of the ligaments, is limited to the range of physiological loads. Therefore, in order to represent the ligaments more accurately, it should be considered the non-physiological loads, which cause soft tissues to damage arising from the tear or plastic deformation of the fibres. So, a model that describes the reduction in the mechanical stiffness of ligaments when non-physiological strains lead to progressive failure of the fibres was used [21]:

$$\Psi = \Psi_{vol} + (1 - D_m)\Psi_{mat} + (1 - D_f)\Psi_{fib} \quad (6)$$

where $D_m \in [0,1]$ is the damage variable for the matrix and $D_f \in [0,1]$ is the damage variable for the fibres. Table 2 shows the parameters used in this work.

Table 2 – Material Properties.

	Type	Parameters	Number of elements (Element type)
Humerus	Rigid body	-	5662 (S4R)
Scapula	Rigid body	-	19775 (S4R)
Articular cartilage	Hyper-elasticity	$C_{10} \approx 1.79$ MPa	5650 (C3D6H)
Glenohumeral capsule	Hyper-elasticity	$C_{10} = 3.82^{-1}$ MPa $k_1 = 1^{-4}$ MPa $k_2 = 5^{-3}$ $k = 5^{-3}$ $\psi_{\max}^f = 3.15^{-1} \sqrt{MPa}$ $\psi_{\min}^f = 5^{-4} \sqrt{MPa}$	1048(C3D8H)

2.3. Simulations

Simulations were run in the presence of bipolar lesions and these comprised 3 steps: pre-tension, contact and translation. Since the capsule only acts as a stabilizer of the glenohumeral joint when it is under tension [11], the pre-tension step was to ensure this. In the initial position the cartilages are inside each other, and with the stretching of the capsule, the cartilages separate, creating tension in the capsule. Then, the contact between the two cartilages was promoted, moving the humerus in the medial direction and restricting all other movements. In the final step, the humeral head was translated in the antero-inferior direction (x-axis), and rotation was restricted in all axis. During all the steps of the simulation the scapula was considered static.

3 Results

In order to conclude regarding the size of defects that lead to shoulder dislocation, the distance to dislocation (DTD) and the Stability Ratio were evaluated, as previously done in other studies [3], [17].

The figures below show the DTD obtained for the different positions tested and with different defects combined.

Fig. 3 – DTD for the different combination of defects for the humerus with 45° of abduction and Neutral Rotation.

Fig. 4 – DTD for the different combination of defects for the humerus with 90° of abduction and Neutral Rotation.

Fig. 5 – DTD for the different combination of defects for the humerus with 45° abduction and 40° of external rotation.

Fig. 6 – DTD for the different combination of defects for the humerus with 45° abduction and 60° of external rotation.

Fig. 7 – DTD for the different combination of defects for the humerus with 90° abduction and 40° of external rotation.

Fig. 8 – DTD for the different combination of defects for the humerus with 90° abduction and 60° of external rotation.

For the humerus abducted 45°/90° and with neutral rotation, the DTD is approximately the same for all defects, except for the glenoid defect of 50% combined with any humeral head defect and the glenoid defect of 37.5% combined with a humeral head defect of 44%. However, the DTD for the humerus with 45° abduction is about 0.006 m and for 90° it is about 0.005 m. Therefore, it can be concluded that the humerus is more unstable for higher abduction angles.

When the humerus is externally rotated with 45° of abduction, Hill-Sachs defects have a greater influence on the stability as the external rotation angle increases. But, in general, the DTD did not present very distinct differences between the external rotation of 40° and 60°.

Moreover, when the humerus is externally rotated at 90° of abduction, different data were obtained from what is presented in the literature. In other words, the DTD for the humerus externally rotated 60° was bigger for the glenoid defect of 25% of the glenoid width when compared with DTD obtained for the humerus externally rotated 40°. This can be justified by the fact that it was considered the presence of ligaments, which stabilize the shoulder in upper ranges.

In summary, when the humerus was with neutral rotation, the size of the glenoid defect was the main cause for instability, while the humeral head defects had more influence when the humerus was externally rotated. Therefore, it can be concluded that the glenoid defects lead to translational instability while the humeral head defects lead to rotational defects, as it was also concluded in another study [17].

Moreover, it can be concluded that the influence of Hill-Sachs defects on glenohumeral stability not only depends on its size but also on its location. Therefore, it is important to note that if another method was used to create the defects, the results might have been different.

To evaluate the stability of the glenohumeral joint, it was calculated the stability ratio (r):

$$r = \frac{s}{c} \quad (7)$$

where the compressive force (c) was considered as the force of the humerus against the glenoid during the contact step and the translational force (s) was considered as the force on the humerus that allows its translation in the anterior-inferior direction until a dislocation or subluxation occurs.

The table below shows the stability ratio obtained for each case:

Table 3 - Stability Ratio for combined defects at 45° and 90°.

	Humeral Head Defects				
	Intact	6%	19%	31%	44%
Glenoid defects (45°)	Intact	6%	19%	31%	44%
Intact	0.49	-	-	-	-
12.5%	-	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40
25%	-	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.12
37.5%	-	0.11	0.10	0.08	0.08
50%	-	0.08	0.08	0.05	0
Glenoid defects (90°)	Intact	6%	19%	31%	44%
Intact	0.47	-	-	-	-
12.5%	-	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.26
25%	-	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.13
37.5%	-	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.11
50%	-	0	0	0	0

For a joint without defects, the ratio of 47% and 49% for the abduction angles of 90° and 45°, was obtained, respectively. These values are similar to the ratio of 43% and 44% obtained in the study [22].

It was concluded from these results that the stability ratio did not show big differences as the size of the Hill-Sachs defects got bigger and the obtained values also confirm the fact that the stability of the joint decreases with the increase in the size of the defects. Besides, these values also support the fact that for larger abduction angles the joint is more unstable.

4 Conclusions

The outputs from this work allowed us to conclude that glenoid defects with sizes bigger than 37.5% of the glenoid width can easily lead to shoulder dislocation. So, a bone block on the glenoid should be performed to recover the glenohumeral joint stability. For glenoid defects with sizes between 12.5% and 37.5%, a Bankart repair might be able to restore stability. Finally, a *remplissage* might be recommended to address humeral head defects with sizes bigger than 44%.

It is also important to note that, as in other studies, the creation of the defects took into consideration the same orientation for all the defects. Although this allows reproducibility, it has the limitation of not representing clinical defects.

For future work, it is suggested to add the muscles to the model and evaluate their influence. This, assuming that if the ligaments have been shown to increase stability on upper ranges of abduction, then the muscles may increase stability in the mid- ranges. Besides, the addition of labrum should also contribute to increased stability since it accounts for 10-20% of the stabilizing forces.

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